

EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION OF BEARING BEHAVIOUR OF 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental approach to characterize the bearing behavior of 3D woven composites. Three specific experimental set-ups are developed for this study. The first set-up is a pin bearing test on a flat surface. The second one is a pin bearing test on half-hole surface. The last setup defined is a double-lap bearing test. The influence of the warp direction on the material's behavior and the diameter-to-thickness D/t ratio are studied here. All the tests are multi-instrumented. Damage and failure mechanisms for each configuration are analyzed and discussed. The material behavior on warp direction displays some similarities with what is currently observed on laminates. Nevertheless, after damage onset, double lap bearing setup highlights clear differences with pin-bearing tests in terms of stiffness, load carrying ability and leads to ultimate failure. The bearing response as a function of D/t ratio has also been discussed and the smallest ratio leads to the best performance in terms of bearing strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are extensively used in aeronautical industry. Composites can be found in aerospace engine as well as airframe applications. SAFRAN group is developing a new generation of polymer matrix 3D woven composite which is introduced in engines critical parts and landing gears. This composite displays good out-of-plane properties, increased resistance to impact and reduces significantly failure mechanisms such as delamination which is a limiting failure mechanism for laminates. The 3D woven composite parts are fastened to other composites or metallic structures. Thus, the present work is focused on the study of the behaviour of the SAFRAN 3D woven composite in a mechanically fastened joint. Composites in bolted junctions are known to fail in various modes such as net-tension, shear-out, cleavage and bearing ([1],[2]). Globally, there is a competition between bearing failure which is a progressive failure mode and net-tension and shear-out which are catastrophic failures. Numerous studies on composite laminates subjected to bearing loadings have been carried out and presented in the literature ([1],[3],[4]). These studies provide many relevant experimental methods and insight of the damage and failure mechanisms induced by bearing loadings in laminates. One particular point concerns the definition of the bearing strength. Indeed, since bearing is a progressive damage phenomenon, several definitions are available in the literature ([5],[6],[7]) and based on hole deformation or loss of stiffness in the behaviour. Only very few studies deal with the bearing behaviour of 3D woven composites. Damages developing in such materials under bearing

loading are complex and much less known than in the case of laminates. McClain and Timoshchuk [8] and Warren *et al.* [9] recently investigated bearing behaviour on thin 3D woven composite under single and double shear setups. In this work an experimental study of the mechanical behaviour of the 3D woven composite under bearing loadings is presented. The main objective of this paper is the study of the behaviour of the material on the warp direction as well as the D/t ratio influence on the macroscopic bearing behaviour of the SAFRAN 3D woven composite.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUPS

The investigation is made on a 3D woven composite [10] provided by SAFRAN, which displays hybrid architecture between ply to ply and through thickness configuration. The material presents a dominant fiber volume fraction in the warp direction. The material is supplied by SAFRAN. All the tests presented in the following have been devised and performed at ONERA.

2.1 Tests

Three mechanical setups have been defined in order to properly characterize the materials behavior under bearing loadings. These three setups represent different trade-offs between the simplicity of observation and analysis and the representativeness with respect to actual mechanically fastened joints, such as bolted joints or lugs.

The first setup is a *pin-bearing test on flat surface*. The setup is shown in Figure 1a. It consists in creating bearing damage by means of a cylinder-to-plane contact. This configuration has already been employed by Wu and Sun [11].

The second setup is a *pin-bearing test on half-hole surface*. The setup shown in Figure 1b differs from the first one in creating bearing damage through a cylinder-to-cylinder contact, thus being closer of an actual pinned-joint. This configuration was investigated by Wang *et al.* [12] and Irisarri *et al.* [13] for laminates. Both pin-bearing tests allow the observation of damage development on the surface of the specimen.

The third setup is a double-lap bearing test (see Figure 1c). The double lap configuration is preferred here over single lap configuration since it offers more stability to the setup and avoids flexural effects. Effort introduction in the double lap test is very similar to that of the pin bearing test on a half-hole. Indeed, in both setups, the contact leading to bearing damage growth is a cylinder-to-cylinder contact. Results obtained with these two setups are discussed in section 3.4. The double-lap bearing test allows only poor observation of the damage growth since the surfaces of the specimen are hidden by metallic plates. Only the thickness of the specimen can be observed. Studies on this configuration have been carried out by Xiao *et al.* [4] for laminates and McClain *et al.* [8] for 3D woven composites. Contrary to compressive tests, this tensile test allows the observation of the ultimate failure of the specimen, failure mode depending on the actual geometry of the specimen. Neither lateral clamping nor confinement effects are considered in the present study. The study is focused on shear bearing behaviour of the material.

For all tests, the instrumentation consists of: (i) a LVDT sensor to precisely measure displacement between test machine's hydraulic jaws, (ii) acoustic emission (AE) setups to monitor the damage evolution throughout the test, and (iii) digital image correlation (DIC) setup to carry out the calculation of displacement and strain field on the observed surface of the specimens.

Figure 1: Test configurations. (a) Pin bearing test on flat surface. (b) Pin bearing test on half-hole surface. (c) Double lap bearing test.

2.2 Specimens

Bearing damage propagation and ultimate failure of mechanical joints can be delayed by putting emphasis on the geometric parameters of the structural part. Collings [1] and more recently Okutan [14] have studied the influence of geometrical parameters (see Figure 2) on the behavior of composite laminates under bearing loadings. Collings and Okutan mainly investigated the effects of the width (W), the hole diameter (D), the thickness (t) and the distance to edge (e) on bearing behavior. For instance, it was shown that the failure mode passes from tensile failure to bearing failure if W/D increases (for $W/D > 4$), and that the failure mode switches from shear failure to bearing failure if e/D increases (for $e/D > 3$). Those relevant parameters gave clues in order to properly design the specimens for the test campaign so that bearing damage development could be ensured. Specimens geometrical dimensions of the tests described in this paper are presented in Table 1. Globally, material orientation means that specimens are cut only at 0° which corresponds to the warp tow direction, at 90° which corresponds to the weft tow direction and at 45° with respect to the warp tow direction.

Figure 2: Geometrical parameters a) Pin bearing specimen b) Double lap bearing specimen.

Test type	D _{pin} (mm)	D _{hole} (mm)	W/D	L/D	e/D	t(mm)	Material Orientation
Pin bearing on flat surface	19.97	-	4	4	-	19.6	Warp (0°)
Pin bearing on half-hole surface	11.97	12.00	4	4	-	9.4	Warp (0°)
	11.97	12.00	4	4	-	19.6	Warp (0°)
	19.97	20.00	4	4	-	9.4	Warp (0°)
	19.97	20.00	4	4	-	19.6	Warp (0°)
	29.95	30.01	3	3	-	9.4	Warp (0°)
	29.95	30.01	3	3	-	19.6	Warp (0°)
Double lap bearing	11.97	12.00	3.75	8	3	9.4	Warp (0°)

Table 1: Geometrical dimensions of the specimens.

3 RESULTS

All tests are controlled in displacement with a displacement rate of 0.1 mm/mn. Test machine load cell is 50 kN. All mechanical tests are performed at room temperature. Pin bearing tests are stopped once the behavior displayed by force-displacement curves tends to stabilize. Double-lap tests are led to ultimate failure of the specimens.

3.1 Pin bearing test on flat surface

Damage mechanisms observed for pin-bearing tests on flat surface in the warp direction are shown in Figure 3 for a pin diameter of 20mm. In Figure 3a, in plane-view of the specimen shows that the damage area under the contact zone seems quite localized, which can constitutes a characteristic scenario under bearing loadings for 3D woven composites. Indeed, on laminates, thickness growth is localized but delamination can be spread throughout the specimen. Here, the benefit from the lack of delamination in 3D woven composite due to its specific architecture implies a more localized damage area. A view from above of the specimen is shown on Figure 3b where is observed the damage mechanisms induced by pin-bearing test. A mark made by the pin is noticed. Matrix cracking is observed on areas right under the pin as well as in the areas surrounding the pin. Material pull-out is noticed also on the upper edge of the specimen especially on warp tows. Warp tow/matrix debonding is observed mainly on areas surrounding the pin mark. This mechanism happens since crushing a material result in stress increase on the areas adjacent to the crushing zone.

Figure 3: Damage and failure mechanisms for a 20 mm Pin-bearing test on flat surface. (a) In-Plane View. (b) View from above in warp direction.

From the mechanisms observed, a damage scenario for pin-bearing tests on flat surface can be summarized: Pin contact with the flat surface leads to progressive matrix cracking alongside with increasing mark width. As the test process continues tow-matrix debonding occurs on adjacent areas of the mark. Then, after having carried high loads, failure mechanisms such as material pull-out on the edge of the specimen takes place.

3.2 Pin bearing test on half hole surface

The mechanisms observed at the end of each test are the same regardless of the orientation. Damages and failure mechanisms carried out for a specimen in the warp direction with a 12 mm diameter pin are shown in Figure 4. In plane-view of the specimen shows that damage and failure area are localized consistently to what has been observed for pin-bearing tests on flat surface, see Figure 4a. Hole ovalization is also exhibited. View from above of the specimen's hole features several damage and failure mechanisms, see in Figure 4b. The pin crushing effect on the half-hole induces weft tows distortion throughout the hole. The pin/hole contact surface also covers a wide area of tow (warp of weft) and matrix. Therefore, matrix cracking and intra-warp tow failure are also observed. Material pull-out on the specimen's upper edge is detected. Warp tow failure has also been observed on specimens edge and specimen thickness increased due to tow-resin debonding.

Figure 4: Damage and failure mechanisms for a 12mm pin-bearing test on half-hole surface. (a) In-Plane View. (b) View from above in warp direction.

A damage scenario for pin-bearing tests on half-hole surface can be expressed. Firstly, pin crushing on hole induces matrix cracking as well as ovalization onset on several areas of the hole. Then, for increasing displacement imposed on the pin, weft tow distortion as well as intra-tow failure happens. Eventually, significant failure mechanisms such as warp tow failure and material pull-out are noticed on specimen edge.

Figure 5 shows normalized bearing stress-displacement curve obtained for pin bearing test on half-hole surface performed on warp direction and for the thinner material with a 12 mm diameter pin. The examination of the curve shows some similarities with what is usually observed on laminates. Indeed, there are several steps in the bearing behavior of the specimen. Firstly, the bearing curve is a linear until the first peak in the bearing curve. Only a short non-linear phase is observed prior to the bearing peak. In the following, the first peak in the bearing curve defines the bearing failure. Bearing strength is defined as the stress at bearing failure. After bearing failure, there is a loss of stiffness which progressively leads to the stabilization of the load. In general, the load level after damage onset shows that the material exhibits a capability to carry high loads with increasing damaging effects.

Figure 5: Bearing curve for 12mm pin-bearing test on half-hole surface on warp direction.

For the half hole bearing test made in the warp direction, it is worth mentioning that at the very same moment where the non-linearity appears in the bearing stress-displacement (see Figure 6), cumulated energetic appears and increases continuously throughout the test duration. This progressive energetic growth is very proper to bearing damage with significant damages mechanisms such as tow failure, matrix/tow debonding likely to occur after that loss of linearity.

Figure 6: Cumulated AE energy and bearing curve for a 12mm warp direction pin-bearing test on half-hole surface

Diameter to thickness D/t ratio influence is investigated for pin bearing tests on half-hole surface. Figure 7 shows the variation of bearing strength with D/t ratio. Three hole diameters associated with 2 different thicknesses provides 6 different D/T ratio values. The first observation consists in observing that the smaller diameter for tests performed on the warp direction remains the most efficient in terms of bearing load carrying ability. Moreover, a linear regression is observed for this direction. This is similar to what has been observed on Collings [1] investigations on laminates. It also implies that structural 3D woven composite parts featuring holes subjected to bearing loadings are not complex to design and engineer.

Figure 7: Bearing strength VS D/t ratio for pin-bearing test on half-hole surface for warp direction.

3.3 Double lap Bearing testing

For the double lap bearing test, since those tests are performed till ultimate failure, the mechanisms observed are typical scenarios of a catastrophic failure. For the warp direction specimen presented in Figure 8, bearing damage which is surrounding the upper half hole, leads progressively to shear out failure for increasing strain. That hole displays extended ovalization when compared to the hole size prior to the test. Warp tows surrounding the hole is subjected to compressive failure which leads to increased material thickness in the bearing failure region as it was observed on Warren *et al.* investigations [9]. Tow tensile failure is generated on the hole edge heading toward weft direction. Matrix shear out-cracking is generated on the shear out zone beyond the bearing damage zone. This shear out failure mode seems relevant since the load path at 0° tends to its development.

Figure 8: Damage and failure mechanisms for 12mm double-lap bearing test on warp direction.

A damage scenario for double lap bearing test can be defined. Ovalization onset on the upper half of the hole appears alongside with matrix cracking on areas surrounding the hole. Crushing due to bearing damage progression is developing around the hole with progressive tow buckling leading to tow compressive failure. As test process continues, there is a transition from bearing damage zone to shear out zone where shear out cracks, tow debonding and localized warp tow tensile failure occur.

Bearing stress-displacement curve is presented in Figure 9a for double lap bearing test performed on the thinner material on the warp direction. The examination of the curve shows that the specificity of the double lap test lies in the behavior observed after the first bearing peak. Indeed, instead of observing a slight decrease or stabilization in stiffness after the peak for an increasing displacement, an increase in stiffness is noticed. This increase takes place until a given force and then an ultimate loss of stiffness is observed and corresponds to the specimens' ultimate failure. The material carries high loads till a certain level even if increasing damages occur on the specimen.

Figure 9: Bearing curves for thin 3D woven composite on warp direction:
 a) double lap bearing test b) pin bearing test on half-hole surface

3.4 Comparisons between tests

Pin bearing tests are performed for understanding purposes. The two types of tests both display localized areas of damages with tow failure resulting from local micro-buckling. Material pull-out on the edge of the specimens is common to those two tests. Nevertheless, some differences are noticed between pin bearing test on a flat surface and on a half-hole surface. The out-of-plane expansion of the material on the loaded side of the hole increases with the imposed displacement. This increase tends to be more important for pin-bearing test on flat surface than for pin bearing test on a half-hole. This phenomenon is mostly due to the nature of the contact leading to bearing damages. The stiffness for pin bearing test performed on flat surface is lower than the one performed on half-hole surface. Moreover, pin bearing specimens loaded on half hole surface carry higher loads than that performed on flat surface.

Pin bearing tests on a half hole surface and double lap bearing tests displays similarities as well as notable differences. In terms of similarities, aside from the nature of the contact leading to bearing damages, the bearing stress-displacement curves presented for warp direction materials display similar bearing strength and close stiffness. Test results up to bearing failure are in good agreement between the pin bearing test on half hole and the double lap bearing test. Damages mechanisms such as matrix cracking, tow failure are common between those two types of tests. Nevertheless, differences lie on what happens after the first bearing peak (see Figure 9). Loss of stiffness leading progressively to stabilization is noticed for pin-bearing test. On the opposite short loss of stiffness is followed by an increase for double lap tests till ultimate failure.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents an experimental investigation of the bearing behaviour of a 3D woven composite conceived by SAFRAN. Macroscopic observations of the characteristic damage mechanisms of the material subjected to bearing loadings are shown and discussed. The bearing behavior on warp direction and the D/t ratio influence on the behaviour of the material are investigated. Based on the experimental results obtained, macroscopic damage mechanisms scenarios are the following: matrix cracking, fibre-matrix debonding, important thickness growth due to tow debonding and tow tensile or compressive failure. AE signal activities pointed out that high amplitude damage events occurred in early stages of the test process, which implies that tow damage occurs early on probably due to the likelihood of the pin to crush a portion or an entire tow on the test initiation. Investigations made on warp oriented material underlined the similarities with laminates in terms of force-displacement curves shape. As a benefit, 3D woven composite displays enhanced ability to carry higher loads even after damage onset compared to laminates. This can be explained by its tendency to not delaminate contrary to laminates which display faster ultimate failure. The D/t ratio influence investigation showed that the smallest ratio leads to the best performance in terms of bearing strength and linear regression is observed for warp direction consistently to what is observed for laminates. Future work will emphasize on thorough examination of the damage mechanisms noticed in this study. Through the-thickness investigations and accurate hole ovalization measures will be performed to have a better understanding of the extent of those damages.

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